

THE DEVELOPMENT OF DAMAGE IN CROSS PLYED GRP LAMINATES

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INTRODUCTION

The object of this work was to study damage development in cross-plyed glass-fibre reinforced epoxy-resin laminates (GRP). In particular the phenomenon of *stress whitening*, prior to transverse cracking, which had been reported by previous workers¹ was investigated.

Laminates were fabricated² from 600 tex rovings of 10 μ m diameter E-glass fibres and an anhydride cured epoxy resin (Shell 828 + NMA) using different amounts of an amine accelerator (BDMA) to obtain different degrees of cure. The laminates were formed by winding the roving onto a frame and vacuum impregnating with the liquid resin. These were then cured in an oven for 3 hours at 100°C and post-cured for 3.5 hours at 150°C. This produced high quality laminates which were virtually transparent but had a light amber colour. The laminates were of a [0 90]_s construction, generally 1.5 - 2.0 mm total thickness. Coupons, 230 x 20 mm, were cut from the plates for tensile testing.

GENERAL OBSERVATIONS OF DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

The test pieces were loaded monotonically in tension and were viewed by oblique illumination. A distinct blue colour was apparent before loading commenced. At very low strains (0.1 - 0.2%) a change from blue to magenta and then red was observed. This change was reversed when the load was relaxed. At slightly higher strain (0.2 - 0.4%) the laminate became translucent (*stress whitening*). This whitening became more intense as the strain was increased. It was also partially reversible if the load was removed but after extension to higher strains (~0.4%) it persisted to some extent. A short heat treatment at 100°C was found to restore the clarity of the laminate. The *colour changes* were more intense but the *whitening* less developed in the more highly cross linked laminates (higher BDMA content).

At still higher strains (0.4 - 0.6%) the first transverse cracks were produced in the 90° ply. When these cracks form strain relaxation occurs in the 90° ply over a short distance either side of the crack. This is made visible by the reappearance of a blue colour corresponding to a zone of low strain. A photograph of a typical coupon showing transverse cracking, whitening and relaxed zones is shown in Fig 1. For further discussion of transverse cracking see for instance Bader et al³.

The colour changes and whitening phenomena were considered to be caused by light scattering from micro-damage features within the transverse ply. These have been studied using microscopy and light scattering techniques.

LIGHT SCATTERING EXPERIMENT

These tests were conducted on laminates made with 0.5% BDMA accelerator because these showed the strongest whitening effect. This formulation results in a relatively low degree of cross-linking in the resin.

A test piece was set up as shown in Fig 2 with a Ne-He LASER beam directed through the transparent specimen. Two configurations were used. In the first the beam was directed normal to the test piece axis and a diffraction photograph was taken. The alternative technique was to set the beam at 45° to the specimen axis and measure the intensity of light scattered normal to the beam.

A set of diffraction photographs is shown in Fig 3. The first (3a) shows the pattern formed when the beam is directed normal to the surface of a $[0\ 90]_s$ laminate in the unloaded state. The diamond pattern is due to diffraction from the fibres in the 0° and 90° plies. It is not symmetric because the total 0° ply thickness is more than double that of the central 90° ply. When the coupon was extended in tension the pattern became elongated in the vertical direction (3b) corresponding to diffraction from interfaces or cavities lying parallel to the 90° fibres. On unloading the pattern relaxed but at zero load showed a stronger vertical component than in its original state (3c). It is considered that the development of the vertical feature is probably due to either microcracking in the matrix, between the fibres in the 90° ply or to micro-debonding at or close to these fibres. The patterns also indicate partial *crack closure* on unloading but some residual damage is still apparent.

In the second type of experiment the LASER was directed at 45° and the intensity of the diffracted light normal to the incident beam was measured. Typical results are shown in Fig 4. The intensity is seen to increase rapidly when the applied strain exceeds a threshold of about 0.2%. On unloading, there was first little change and then the intensity dropped, but not to its original value. On reloading through a similar strain range the intensity increased further and the threshold was depressed. These results lead to conclusions which are consistent with those drawn from the diffraction patterns.

A further experiment was to heat treat the specimen at 120°C after testing and then retesting. This showed that the damage was *virtually "repaired"* by heating for as short a period as 20 min. This is shown in Fig 5 where the light-scattering threshold is actually seen to increase after the treatment. The damage/repair cycle may be repeated several times with progressive increases in the threshold strain. This implies that not only is the damage *repaired* but resistance to further damage is increased, probably due to further advancement of the *state of cure* of this resin. Crack healing in polymers has been reported by a number of workers ie Wool and O'Connor⁴.

MICROSTRUCTURE MICROSCOPIC STUDIES

Conclusive evidence of the reversibility of damage on heat treatment was provided by optical microscopy of the polished edge of test pieces. An arrangement using transmitted light was found to be the most sensitive for the detection of fine scale damage.

Figure 6a shows the structure of the 90° ply prior to loading. Some cracks are visible; these are due to thermal stresses. At zero load but after straining to 0.45% (6b) many additional microcracks are visible. These appear to be concentrated in regions of high fibre packing and to be generally tangential to the fibre surface and normal to the tension axis. After heat treatment at 100 °C for 30 (6c) minutes most of these microcracks are no longer visible although the original thermal cracks are still to be seen.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work has shown that micro-damage occurs in [0 90]_s glass-fibre/epoxy-resin laminates at strains well below those at which transverse cracks are observed. The latter have been generally regarded as the first failure events in multi-axial laminates. In the laminates studied, the micro-damage consists mainly of matrix cracks of the order of 1 - 10 µm width, tangential to and between the fibres in the more closely packed regions of the 90° ply, although some debonding around fibres has also been observed. It has been shown that these matrix cracks, in a low cure laminate, can be *healed* by heat-treatment for short periods at 100°C. This *healing* ability may be related to the state of cure of the resin and may occur only in systems which are initially undercured; as was the case with the resin used in this work. This confirms the earlier work of Parvizi⁵. The resistance to crack growth is also seen to increase with increasing cure. The techniques used to observe and monitor the colour changes and stress-whitening are unfortunately only applicable to laminates that are transparent to light.

REFERENCES

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Fig. 1 Photograph of a portion of a 20 mm wide tensile test piece of $[0,90]_s$ GRP laminate. The transverse cracks appear white and can be seen to initiate from the free edges of the coupon. The background shows extensive stress-whitening except for the stress relieved regions either side of the transverse cracks which appear dark.

Fig. 2 The test configuration for the LASER diffraction experiments. The diffraction patterns were obtained with the LASER beam arranged normal to the specimen axis and the scattered light measurements made using the 45° arrangement.

3a

3b

3c

Fig. 3 This shows 3 diffraction patterns. The first (3a) is for the unloaded $[0,90]_s$ laminate which gives an asymmetric diamond pattern. Upon tensile extension (3b) the vertical component extends dramatically due to the formation of interfaces, or cavities, parallel to the 90° fibres. On relaxation of the load (3c) most of the cavities close up but some residual damage is still apparent.

Fig. 4 Graph showing the variation of the scattered light intensity, I_s , vs strain for a [0,90]_s GRP laminate cured with 0.5% BDMA. On first extension the intensity rises sharply when the strain exceeds the light scattering threshold, a. When the load is relaxed the intensity decreases, b-c-d, but remains above the initial level. On reloading the threshold, e, is depressed and it rises to a higher level, f, than in the first cycle.

Fig. 5 The response to thermal treatments for a similar laminate is shown. Curve A is the relationship observed when the coupon is first loaded. After unloading and heating at 120° for 30 min the threshold is increased as shown in B. A further cycle of unloading and heat treatment leads to curve C. This indicates that the "damage" has been completely repaired by each heat treatment. The increase in the threshold from 0.2 - 0.3% strain is attributed to further curing of the resin.

6a

6b

6c

100 μ m

Fig. 6 These are 3 photomicrographs each of the same area of the 90° ply at the free-edge of a tensile coupon. The first (6a) shows the structure before the application of any load. The cracks visible are probably due to thermal stress. On loading to a strain of 0.45% and then unloading to zero stress (6b) extensive microcracking is observed but most of this is healed when the test piece is heated at 120° for 30 min (6c).